

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

Reza Ahmadiansah¹, Rafidhul Misbah², Yuli Nur Ariyani³

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Da'wah, Salatiga State Islamic University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: For every individual who has entered adolescence, they have determined their future orientation and have a focus regarding their future goals in life, one of which is in education. This study aims to determine the level of parental support for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego Boyolali, the level of future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego Boyolali and the influence of parental support on adolescents' future educational orientation in Sumber Agung Village, Klego Boyolali. This type of research is correlational quantitative research. The sample in this study was adolescents aged 16 to 18 years who were still in school and domiciled in Sumber Agung Village, totaling 69 youths. The data source in this study used a scale of parental support and a scale of future education orientation. The results showed that, first, parental support for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego Boyolali was in the high category with a percentage of 56.53%. Second, the future education orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali was in the high category with a percentage of 65.22%. Third, the influence of parental support on the future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung village, Klego, Boyolali with an Fcount of 32,740 with a significance level of 0.000 <0.05; R square is 0.328 and the coefficient of determination is 32.8%. Thus the hypothesis that says "is there an influence of parental support on the future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village" is accepted.

KEYWORDS: parental support, future education orientation, adolescents

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the important things in human life in the era of globalization, because education is used as a means of self-development to form better human beings. Is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students are able to actively develop their potential to become religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by the community, nation and country[1].

Education creates and helps support to achieve a more advanced and directed life. They consider education to be an important matter for preparation, when entering the world of work and interacting with their social environment, so that education is one of the future plans of every human being, especially someone who has entered their teens.

Future orientation is a form of cognitive development that occurs in adolescents[2]. Future orientation is an effort made to predict the future, where a person begins to seriously think about his future education[3].

There are three processes in forming a future orientation, including (1) Motivation is something that leads to interests, motives and goals related to one's hopes and aspirations in the future. (2) Planning is something that refers to the planning, actions, and strategies to realize the hopes and ideals to be achieved. (3) Evaluation is something that refers to the extent to which expectations can be realized[4]. The evaluation phase provides an opportunity for individuals to make improvements to the goals and plans that have been made, even if they do not materialize as expected.

Future orientation is a picture of a person's way of thinking and acting regarding conditions in the future and the results to be achieved[5]. Says future orientation is a description of how a person sees himself in the future[6]. Say future orientation is behavior that has a purpose regarding one's perspective of the future[7].

Say future orientation is an action taken by a person regarding how the individual sees himself or another individual by involving cognitive aspects in describing and preparing for the future, as well as actions taken to achieve expectations and goals in the form of activities that are in accordance with the needs and determination of an individual[7].

Future orientation is very important for teenagers who have entered high school, because teenagers are required to be able to make decisions and make choices about their future. In making decisions regarding future orientation, adolescents definitely need help, guidance and support from their families, especially their father and mother. Parents are really needed in decision-making, support and advice that can have a long-term effect on adolescents who are determining their future orientation.

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

Parental support is support that leads to actions taken by a person to another person in the form of a sense of concern, appreciation, or in the form of assistance that is needed and felt[8]. Parental support is support that has factors to influence children's motivation in learning[9]. Said that parental support can also be said to be an important form of social support, especially for children who have entered their teenage years[10].

Parental support is an attitude, an act of family acceptance of family members, in the form of informational support, research support, instrumental support and emotional support[11]. Says parental support is a provision of assistance and motivation given by parents to children both in the form of words and actions[12].

Parental support involves four supports including (1) Emotional or esteem support is support that calls for feelings of empathy, caring, concern, positive appreciation or warmth and motivation given by someone to others. (2) Tangible instrumental support is support given by a person directly to another person in the form of action, such as assistance in the form of finance/finance and assistance when having difficulty doing work. (3) Informational support is support given by someone in the form of giving advice, directions, advice, or input related to problems or actions taken by someone. (4) Companionship support is support related to one person's availability for other people to spend time by providing reinforcement in the form of entertaining and rewarding[8].

Said parental support is support provided by parents in the form of information, attention, encouragement, appreciation that has an emotional effect or an action effect that can later solve problems[13]. Then the opinion above is reinforced by the opinion which says that parental support is awareness related to the responsibility to educate and nurture children by providing assistance, attention, a sense of security and comfort and realizing it with help finance[14].

From the conclusions of the opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that parental support is an action taken by parents towards children in the form of attention, caring, giving a sense of trust, advising or providing suggestions and meeting the needs of children, while the orientation of future education is orientation, goals and expectations related to the future of education that someone wants to achieve in the future by going through three main psychological stages, such as motivation, planning and evaluation.

Based on the explanation above, the writer aims to find out: (1) The level of parental support for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali, (2) The level of future education orientation for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali, (3) Whether there is an influence of parental support on the future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali.

II. METHODS

Research design

The type of research used is quantitative research using statistical tests[15]. The approach in this study uses a correlational approach to the causal relationship category[16]. In determining the sampling technique the author uses non-random sampling or the subject does not have the same opportunity to be sampled[17]. The author uses the research method above, because it is based on the purpose of this study, which is to reveal the effect of parental support on future educational orientation in adolescents in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village, where the researcher wants the research to be carried out systematically and objectively so that the data obtained is concrete, measurable and rational.

Participant

The sample in this study used adolescents with the following criteria: (1) still attending school at the SMK/SMA/MA level, (2) domiciled in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali, (3) ages ranging from 16 to 18 years. The sample calculation technique uses the Slovin formula with a population of 216 teenagers by calculating the Slovin formula with an error of 10%, so that the total sample used is 69 teenagers. Below is the sample calculation using the Slovin formula:

$$n = N / N. \alpha^2 + 1$$

Information: N: Number of Samples N: Total Population e: Significance or error level of 10% (Putri, 2013: 17). Based on the formula above, the number of samples determined in the study is as follows: $n = 216 / 216. 10\%^2 + 1$ $n = 216 / 3.16 = 68.35 = 69$ subjects. Then the sample used in this study were 69 respondents.

In this study consisted of 2 questionnaires used. The two questionnaires were made directly by the authors and then expert judgment was carried out by six psychologists. The two questionnaires include: parental support scale and future education orientation scale with each scale having 45 items. The instrument in this study used a Likert scale with four categories "strongly agree", "agree", "disagree", "strongly disagree". Instrument testing in this study went through three stages, including: (1) validation test using the Aiken's V table, experiencing 13 items for each instrument, so that the number of items per instrument is 32 items. (2) the reliability test using chronbach's alpha yielded a score of 0.920 for the parental support instrument, while the future education orientation instrument was 0.889. (3) discriminatory power with item selection criteria based on the total item correlation, which is $r_{iX} > 0.30$ (Azwar, 2020). It is known that at this stage, the items experienced a fall back as many as 4 items from each instrument, so that the total items per instrument were 28 items.

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

Data Analysis Techniques Data analysis techniques in this study used descriptive statistical tests through two classic assumption tests, namely the normality test with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test of Normality with the SPSS version 25 program. Then the linearity test used the SPSS version 25 program with a significance level value of 0.05.

III. RESULTS

Characteristics of respondents

Total respondents in this study were 69 teenagers. The details of the respondent's character will be explained in the tables below:

Table1. Characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	Amount	Percentage
Gender		
Man	30	43%
Woman	39	57%
Age		
16		57%
17		41%
18		2%

Based on Table 1 above, it is known that the most respondents were female respondents with a total of 39 and the percentage was 57%, while the most age-based respondent characters were at the age of 16 years with a percentage of 57%.

Data analysis

Below will be presented the results of the analysis of data obtained on the level of parental support and future orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali:

Table 2. Category of Parental Support Score

Category	Interval	N	Percentage
High	84-112	39	56,53%
Medium	56-84	30	43,47%
Low	28-56	0	0%
Amount	-	69	100%

Based on the above categories, the results of parental support are found in the high category, between the intervals of 84 to 112 with the number of respondents 39 and the percentage being 56.53%.

Table 3. Categories of future Education Orientation

Category	Interval	N	Percentage
High	84-112	45	65,22%
Medium	56-84	24	34,78%
Low	28-56	0	0%
Amount	-	69	100%

Based on the above categories, it shows that the results of future education orientation are in the high category, between the interval 84 to 112 with the number of respondents 45 and the percentage 65.22%.

Classic assumption test

Before testing the hypothesis using simple linear regression, the resecher conducted two stages of testing the classical assumptions as a requirement before testing the hypothesis. In the following, the results of the classical assumption test process will be explained.

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

Table 4. Normality Test Results

		Dukungan Orang Tua	Orientasi Pendidikan Masa Depan
N		69	69
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	85.88	88.30
	Std. Deviation	8.796	8.467
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.081	.089
	Positive	.076	.062
	Negative	-.081	-.089
Test Statistic		.081	.089
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}	.200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.
 b. Calculated from data.
 c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
 d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Based on the table above, it shows that the parental support questionnaire has a sig value of = 0.200 and the future education orientation questionnaire has a sig value of = 0.200. So from the two p values above it can be concluded that the significance value of the two variables shows a p value of $0.200 > 0.05$ from the significance level, so that the two questionnaires are said to be normally distributed.

Table 5. Linearity Test Results

ANOVA Table			Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Orientasi Pendidikan Masa Depan *	Between Groups	(Combined)	3153.1	32	98.537	2.06	.018
Dukungan Orang Tua	Linearity		1600.1	1	1600.1	33.4	.000
	Deviation from Linearity		1553.0	31	50.099	1.04	.443
	Within Groups		1721.4	36	47.817		
			17				
	Total		4874.6	68			
			09				

Based on the significance score (sig) from the results of the table calculation above, the value of the deviation from linearity is 0.443 which is greater than the stipulated sig value of 0.05. So it can be said that there is a linear influence between the parental support variable (X) and the future education orientation variable (Y), so that the results of the linearity test above are considered to have a linear relationship or the two variables lie in a straight line.

Hypothesis testing

To find out the influence of the independent variable (parental support) on the dependent variable (future education orientation) using a summary model table analysis. Below are the results of the test using the summary model table.

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

Table 6. Analysis Test Results of Table Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.573 ^a	.328	.318	6.991

a. Predictors: (Constant), Parental Support

Based on the table above, it is known that the correlation or relationship (R) is 0.573 with an adjusted R Square score of 0.318, so from the output the R Square coefficient of determination is 0.328. So it can be concluded that the effect of the independent variable (parental support) on the dependent variable (future education orientation) is 32.8%.

Table 7. Anova Analysis Test Results

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1600.116	1	1600.116	32.740	.000 ^b
Residual	3274.493	67	48.873		
Total	4874.609	68			

a. Dependent Variable: Future Education Orientation
b. Predictors: (Constant), Parental Support

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the score of F count = 32,740 with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05. Then there is an influence between parental support (X) and future education orientation (Y), so that the regression model can be used to predict parental support and future education orientation.

Table 8. the results of simple linear regression analysis

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t
1	(Constant)	40.940	8.320		4.920
	Dukungan Orang Tua	.551	.096	.573	5.722

a. Dependent Variable: Orientasi Pendidikan Masa Depan

Constant value (a) shows a number of 40,940, while the value of parental support (b/regression coefficient) is 0.551, so it can be concluded that the regression equation is written as follows:

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$Y = 40.940 + 0.551X$$

The above equation can be explained as follows:

a. A constant of 40,940 means that the consistency value of future education orientation is 40,940.

b. The regression coefficient X shows the number 0.551, then the value of parental support is 0.551 which indicates the regression coefficient is positive and it can be said that the direction of the influence of variable X on Y is positive.

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the t value is 5,722 with a significance level of 0.00. So according to the provisions of the p-value, if the significance value is > 0.05 the hypothesis is rejected otherwise if the significance value is < 0.05 the hypothesis is accepted. In the table above the significance value is 0.00 < 0.05, so the hypothesis is accepted so that it can be said that parental support can influence the future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali.

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

IV. DISCUSSION

1. The level of parental support for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali.

Based on the results of the study, it was found that parental support for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village was in the high category of 56.53% and had a frequency of 39 subjects.

Parental support is very much needed by adolescents, moreover this support from parents, because with support it can help adolescents feel more confident, comfortable and feel accompanied by someone when the adolescent experiences difficulties and problems.

2. The level of future education orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

Based on the results of the study it was found that the future education orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village was in the high category of 65.22% and had a frequency of 45 subjects.

Future education orientation is a plan made by someone related to their future education, the better the orientation of future education one has, the person already has a mature plan for his future. On the other hand, if someone is lacking and is still confused about planning for the future, it can be said that the orientation of his future education is low, so that there is a need for direction and guidance from teachers, friends and family, especially parents.

3. The influence of parental support on future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali.

Based on the results of the above study, the Fcount score shows a number of 32,740 with a significance level of $0.00 < 0.05$, so it can be said that there is an influence between the parental support variable (X) and the future education orientation variable (Y). Furthermore, the correlation value (R) is 0.573 with a determinant score R square of 0.328, so it can be concluded that the influence of parental support variables on future education orientation variables is 32.8% and in the simple linear regression coefficient table shows a significance level value of 0.00, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis of the effect of parental support on future educational orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali is accepted. Basically, parental support for future educational orientation is needed. The lack of support from parents can have an effect on their future orientation, including adolescents feeling they do not have support in the form of affection, understanding and assistance in the form of material. So that teenagers feel alienated from their parents.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the data that has been tested and collected, it can be concluded that the level of parental support for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali, the level of future education orientation for adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali is in the high category and the influence of parental support towards the future education orientation of adolescents in Sumber Agung Village, Klego, Boyolali, the hypothesis is accepted.

REFERENCES

- 1) P. Prayitno, A. Afdal, I. Idfil, and Z. Ardi, "Layanan Bimbingan Kelompok dan Konseling Kelompok yang Berhasil: Dasar dan Profil," 2017.
- 2) Desmita, *Psikologi perkembangan*. PT Remaja Rosdakarya, 2013.
- 3) S. W. Hadianti and H. Krisnani, "Penerapan metode orientasi masa depan (OMD) pada remaja yang mengalami kebingungan identitas (menentukan tujuan hidup)," *Share: Social Work Journal*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 81–89, 2017.
- 4) J.-E. Nurmi, "How do adolescents see their future? A review of the development of future orientation and planning," *Developmental review*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–59, 1991.
- 5) Y. Nopirda, O. Oktivianto, and N. R. Dhevi, "Hubungan self esteem dan orientasi masa depan bidang pendidikan pada siswa kelas XI di Palembang," *Jurnal pendidikan glasser*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 107–116, 2020.
- 6) R. Susanti, "Gambaran orientasi masa depan remaja dalam bidang pekerjaan ditinjau dari religiusitas dan motivasi berprestasi pada remaja Desa Sei Banyak Ikan Kelayang," *Jurnal Psikologi*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 109–116, 2016.
- 7) A. A. Kennedy, Y. Maputra, and D. Puspasari, "Orientasi Masa Depan Pada Remaja Pelaku Tindak Pidana," *Psycho Idea*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 63–73, 2020.
- 8) E. P. Sarafino and T. W. Smith, *Health psychology: Biopsychosocial interactions*. John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- 9) S. Nuranti, "Pengaruh Dukungan Orang Tua Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Peserta Didik Pada Mata Pelajaran Akuntansi Kelas Xi Iis Di Sma Negeri 11 Makassar," *Ekonomi*, 2019.
- 10) A. Amila, J. Sinaga, and E. Sembiring, "Self efficacy dan gaya hidup pasien hipertensi," *Jurnal Kesehatan*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 360–365, 2018.
- 11) Y. Yuliya, "Hubungan Antara Dukungan Orangtua Dengan Motivasi Belajar Pada Remaja," *Psikoborneo: Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2019.
- 12) A. Diniaty, "Dukungan Orangtua terhadap Minat Belajar Siswa," *Jurnal Al-Taujih: Bingkai Bimbingan Dan Konseling Islami*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 90–100, 2017.

Parental Support for Adolescents' Future Education Orientation in Sumber Agung Klego Boyolali Village

- 13) A. Asna, "Hubungan Regulasi Diri Dan Dukungan Orang Tua Dengan Prokrastinasi Mahasiswa Fakultas Dakwah Dan Komunikasi Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara," 2020.
- 14) I. P. P. B. D. Putra, N. W. Suniasih, and I. B. S. Manuaba, "Determinasi motivasi belajar dan dukungan orang tua terhadap minat baca," *International Journal of Elementary Education*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 26–34, 2020.
- 15) S. Azwar, "Metode penelitian psikologi," *Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar*, 2017.
- 16) D. Sugiyono, "Prof, Statistika Untuk Penelitian," *Bandung: Alfabeta Bandung*, 2017.
- 17) J. Periantalo, "Penelitian kuantitatif untuk psikologi," *Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar*, vol. 186, 2016.